

CHARACTERISTICS OF ORGANIZING SPORTS HEALTH TOURISM ACTIVITIES IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *In the content of this article, methodical instructions and practical recommendations are given for conducting sports tourism activities, suitable natural geographical places, which are important in the formation and development of internal sports-health tourism types for different levels of students. There are also issues of taking into account the natural conditions of the seasonal characteristics of the places in the organization of sports health tourism.*

Key words: *tourism, domestic tourism, sports tourism, mountain tourism, water tourism, tourism, bicycle tourism, auto tourism, horse tourism, air tourism, tourism activities, travel, guide, exotic, equipment (rope, ax, pallet, rucksack).*

Introduction to the work. In our republic, a number of reforms are being implemented to develop the tourism sector, expand the tourist and related infrastructure in the regions, produce tourist equipment and create new tourism facilities, and significant positive results are being achieved. Appendix 1 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5611 dated January 5, 2019 "On additional measures for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" in the "Concept for the development of the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025" defines important tasks aimed at the development of tourism in the country given For example, it is established to develop special programs for the development of domestic tourism. Today, field practices and various sports and health tourism trainings are organized for students of geography, history, physical education and tourism.

Therefore, as one of the means of raising the young generation to become a physically fit and spiritually mature person, great attention is paid to the development of domestic sports-health tourism, and elements of sports tourism are used in this.

The relevance of the work. Mass development of a healthy lifestyle in our republic by attracting different segments of the population to sports and wellness tourism.

Comment: The relevance of the topic is that sports and health tourism means, first of all, a path to health. It has been proven that traveling, watching nature, breathing fresh oxygen-rich air, and ultraviolet rays of the sun are more beneficial to a person than taking medicine in the treatment of some diseases. Traveling, walking more is an important remedy for people, and it is being used in medicine as the most important means of preventing and getting rid of diseases.

Purpose of work. Mass introduction of sports tourism in various educational institutions of our republic and to different population groups.

Public formation of a healthy lifestyle by involving in sports-health tourism, identification of places that cure various diseases, medicinal mountain plants on walks, climatic features and new sports-health places of our country.

Tasks of the work. By engaging in sports-health tourism in the fresh air away from big cities, it is necessary to strengthen the health of various population groups, to form their will, and to refresh their psyche, to ensure that they collect the necessary energy for vital activity through sports-health tourism.

In our country, it is implemented by forming a healthy lifestyle, involving the population in physical education and mass sports. Sports and health tourism is very important in the implementation of this promotion.

The implementation of the law on tourism, adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 16, 2019 and approved by the Senate on June 21, 2019. and the relevance of the work was selected based on the law on the certification of the qualifications of the guides.

Tourism is being developed in different directions in different countries. While several countries are achieving this through large expenditures, others are achieving this through the use of the natural resources of this place. It is not an exaggeration that attracting tourists through several destinations and developing different projects can bring a lot of income to any country. That is why the issues of complex organization of tourist trips are becoming more urgent. Especially, the presence of natural conditions is a positive incentive to make these trips. Currently, sports and health tourism has a special place in the concept of sustainable development of many countries. International experts pay particular attention to the importance of sports and wellness tourism in the development of various regions. There are many opportunities for the development of various branches of sports and health tourism in the rural areas of Jizzakh region.

Currently, Uzbekistan is losing in the competition of international sports and wellness tourism. Based on this, we should start targeted and systematic actions regarding the necessary activities for the development of this field, making extensive use of our places with favorable natural geographical conditions, which can be the center of international sports and wellness tourism.

Walks and trips form a person's physical education, culture, intelligence and coordination of actions. Our country offers many opportunities for extreme sports due to its vast and varied landscapes, although these sports are still relatively new in the country.

The nature of Uzbekistan serves as a very comfortable place for lovers of active recreation.

The result of the scientific instruction of the work. As a result of the research, studying the literature and summarizing them, it is possible to divide sports and health tourism activities into the following types:

Hiking mountain tourism. First of all, a person engaged in this tourism improves blood circulation in the body by walking, the person is alive with oxygen, the mountain air is saturated with fresh oxygen, saturates the body with oxygen, and the body receives the necessary nutrients (vitamin D) in the morning sunlight. Among its beautiful scenery One-day and multi-day trekking, mountain climbing, visits to mountain caves, breathtaking views of mountain peaks at an altitude of 3000 to 4000 meters, traditional remote mountain villages with warm and hospitable people, rare flora, endemic and rare endangered animals. , beautiful waterfalls, mountain lakes and torrential mountain rivers should be highlighted. Mountain tourism - alpinism, cave tourism - speleology, and the trips of the travelers who have special training for such trips to conquer mountain peaks and explore caves.

The mountains of Uzbekistan are a very attractive place for lovers of active recreation such as mountaineering, mountain tourism and rock climbing. Most of the country's territory is occupied by plains, but in many regions of the country there are also chains of the Tien-Shan and Pamir mountain ranges stretching from west to east.

One of the famous mountainous regions of Uzbekistan is the Chimyon mountains, the highest peak of which is the 3309-meter Katta Chimyon peak. This area is home to many hiking trails, rock climbing trails, horseback riding trails, cross-country ski trails, and more. There are three ski resorts - Chimyon, Bildirsoy and Amirsoy, which attract lovers of various winter sports. The ski season runs from late December to mid-March. The best time for downhill skiing is February.

Deep caves such as the Boysun spring (amplitude 1415 m), festivalnaya-Ledopadnaya (-580 m) and Ural (-565 m) in the Boysun mountain range, wonderful views of the Kulasoy, Langar and Gulkam gorges, the healing air of the northwestern rocks of the Turkestan mountain range in Zomin - is among the places that can attract an unprecedented number of tourists and thrill seekers.

Water tourism. Uzbekistan is one of the few landlocked countries, but nevertheless has many water areas for water sports tourism - these are the deep water basin of Chervoq in the foothills of the Western Tien Shan, countless flood rivers and the huge sea-like Aydarkol, Sudoche and Tashkent. lakes like the sea. While relaxing here, you can ride a wind speed scooter or explore the surroundings on a catamaran. For those who like extreme recreation, many tour operators offer rafting on rivers such as Chotkal, Pskem, Ugam, Syrdaryo and many other places. Water tourism, diving, that is, going on a boat, yacht, trip to water bodies in special equipment, exploring the world of underwater plants and animals also gives a person a special pleasure.

Air tourism. With air tourism in Uzbekistan, you can fly a paraglider almost any time of the year, the only limitation is rain, because the wing of the paraglider is made of fabric. The most popular time of the year is summer, and the best place to fly is the mountains of the country. The most popular place for paragliding is the surroundings of the Chervoq reservoir, located 60 km from Tashkent. You can fly with a professional instructor or independently after special training. In addition to paragliding, there are also enough natural conditions to travel in a hot air balloon. During the flight, a wonderful view of the reservoir and the surrounding mountain peaks will open, and the human body and senses will be able to enjoy the beauty of nature from above.

Horse tourism. An increasing number of tourists visit Uzbekistan to engage in the sport of equestrian tourism, to see famous pedigree, pure-bred Uzbek horses, to watch national equestrian competitions, and to experience the incomparable joy of riding thoroughbred horses to our bodies and temperaments.

It is known from history that since the 11th century BC, war horses were taken out of the Fergana (Davon) valley for the army of the Chinese emperor along the Silk Road, which indicates the development of equestrian sports, horse tourism and attention to horses in Uzbekistan. In a beautiful valley not far from the city of Tashkent, at the foot of Big and Little Chimyon, at an altitude of 1600 meters, there is a resort complex "Chimyon Rest" intended for lovers of horse sports. Here you can walk around the beautiful surroundings of the resort. Experienced instructors now teach beginners how to handle horses, while experienced riders can improve their skills.

Tourists are surprised by the number of horse clubs that exist in the country, there are more than fifteen of them. They are located in the city of Tashkent and its surroundings, in Fergana, Kashkadarya and other regions.

The journey through the mountain, whose clean and transparent air is filled with the fragrance of countless herbs and flowers, and the romantic dinner around the fire under the bottomless mountain sky, full of thousands of stars, will remain in the memory for a long time.

Bicycle tourism. Bicycle tourism in Uzbekistan is considered a type of tourism rich in exotic, legendary and oriental hospitality. The season starts in mid-April and lasts until November. Cycling tours can be combined with a trip along the Great Silk Road, a trip to the ancient cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and Termiz, as well as a trip through exciting mountain landscapes and flower valleys. Cyclists can experience the lifestyle of local people as they travel through villages and mountain villages. For those who like extreme sports, there is a route along the Oktog range near Samarkand, which can offer a very exciting feeling.

Instructional recommendations of work. Tourism activities held in educational institutions are organized using the forms of trips to the heart of nature with children and trips to urban or rural cultural centers, museums and historical monuments, recreational parks, swimming pools.

The route of the trip is determined before the training sessions. The management of local places of residence, the departments of internal affairs and the rescue department are notified in writing about the date, direction, duration, and participants of the trip.

The participants of the traveling groups will be selected. Groups can be from 6 to 15 people. Travelers are expected to be from 2 to 5 groups. They are appointed leaders from teachers and trainers.

The responsibilities of travelers during the trip are clearly defined. A cook, a doctor, rescue specialists are involved in the trips. Farm equipment, tents, overnight equipment, cooking equipment, rescue equipment are made.

The following rules shall be observed when organizing and defining the tasks of travel groups when conducting tourism trainings, excursions, trips.

The purpose and task of trips, the direction of trips are determined. It is important to take into account the age and physical fitness of children.

Travel directions are set to mountains, rivers, lakes and sea shores, forests, because the main health-improving task of the trip is provided by places with favorable geographical conditions, and a topographic map is prepared.

Specially trained groups are allowed to go on trips in winter and in the season with many natural phenomena.

Taking into account the natural disasters that may occur during the trip, it is absolutely necessary to seriously prepare for rescue work and first aid in case of negative incidents such as injuries.

It is necessary to divide the responsibilities of travelers in tour groups, guide, guide, mover at the end of the line, cook and doctor's assistants, responsible for household equipment, organizers of public events, responsible people with understanding and knowledge related to this tour are determined depending on the type of tour.

Preparing the necessary equipment for the trip: travel clothes, hats and shoes are selected according to the season and the nature of the trip.

Luggage bags are selected according to the age and physical fitness of travelers, they should be waterproof, have many pockets, and should be easy to open and close. Extra clothes,

hygiene products, washing equipment, towels, eating equipment, first aid equipment, needle, thread, writing instruments, camera, literature, binoculars, flashlight and other accessories and weapons are prepared depending on the type of hiking.

Learning how to make travel tents, sleeping bags, farm tools, food products, equipment for public events, and how to prepare and use communication tools is not without purpose.

Walking around in the beautiful nature, in the fresh air, preparing and eating delicious food while relaxing, having a conversation with a group around a bonfire in the heart of nature, of course, if you listen to a beautiful song under the guitar music during the conversation, the walk will be interesting and enjoyable, the body will be strong, and the mood will be at a high level. and a process was formed that would ensure saturation with strong psychological energy.

Practical work recommendations. When children are involved in tourism activities, they should undergo a medical check-up. Children of all ages can be attracted to trips to urban and rural cultural centers, museums and historical monuments, parks, swimming pools.

Preparation of travel equipment, selection of clothes and shoes, preparation of bags and tents, formation of theoretical knowledge about tourism and travel, watching films and videos about travel and travel destinations, animal and plant life, national heritage, historical monuments, homeland and about its history, organizing evenings about famous scholars, meetings with experienced travelers, mentors, teaching young children about the ways of traveling, moral qualities, friendship, brotherhood, community, courage, organization, fairness, honesty, etc. are formed.

Special preparatory training for travelers is the formation of physical movement skills and abilities, the development and improvement of physical qualities, that is, the formation of special theoretical and practical knowledge and skills in travelers.

Sleeping areas are cleaned of dry branches, stones and pieces. Bounded by symbols or flags. The rules for choosing and preparing a place for setting up single, double and multi-person tents, as well as for erecting tents, are followed. Tents are installed against the direction of the wind.

Places are chosen to sit and chat, make bonfires. It is necessary to observe technical safety rules for cooking public food or when lighting an independent campfire. In this case, it is appropriate that the bonfire should not be in the forest, and the hearths should be surrounded by stone walls. It is advisable to use long-burning fatty wood for the bonfire.

Summary. In the years of independence, special attention was paid to the development of physical education and sports-health improvement activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Sufficient legal-regulatory documents have been developed for the implementation of these works and their implementation has been ensured. The tourism sector is one of the fastest growing sectors of the world economy. Its comprehensive development is becoming a source of great income for many countries, especially for Uzbekistan.

Measures taken by our government to ensure the implementation of decrees, laws and decisions on the further development of tourism serve the sustainable development of this direction in our country. Based on these reforms, we can say that the development of sports and health tourism in our country is an important factor in strengthening the health of students.

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